

Preliminary Mapping of Phytocoenological Communities of Forests in the Republic of Croatia Using Remote Sensing Methods

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Abstract: In forestry practice, phytocoenology plays a vital role as it enables the classification of forests into different plant communities and provides a clear insight into their composition, developmental stages, and various ecological and biological characteristics. Phytocoenology offers essential guidelines to foresters who manage existing forest stands, helping them select appropriate silvicultural techniques and forest structures that most efficiently utilize the natural potential of the habitat. A high-quality map of phytocoenological communities simplifies management and supports the selection of silvicultural techniques as well as monitoring the condition of individual phytocoenological communities. Using remote sensing methods, with a strong emphasis on satellite imagery that provides a large amount of spatiotemporal data, an analysis will be conducted for the purpose of mapping phytocoenological communities. Based on analyses of land Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 satellite image classifications, existing phytocoenological maps of questionable spatial accuracy will be improved, and new maps representing the current state will be created with current accuracy of developed models sitting at 57% accuracy. This work, as part of the ALCAR project, will contribute to the management of Croatian forest phytocoenological communities and raise awareness of possible changes within them.

Keywords: forest communities; phytocoenology; phytocoenological communities; remote sensing.

1 Introduction

Phytocoenology (or plant sociology) studies the life, structure, and development of plant communities as they interact with their habitats and each other (Vukelić and Rauš 1998). Emerging from plant geography in the late 19th century, the discipline established its methodological foundations in the early 20th century, eventually branching into specialized fields like forestry phytocoenology. Beyond its theoretical importance, it is essential for ecosystem restoration, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable resource management in the face of climate change. In recent decades, satellite remote sensing has revolutionized the field. Systems like Landsat, MODIS, and Sentinel-2, along with the Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 (HLS) dataset, enable high-resolution, continuous forest monitoring (Wulder et al. 2022, Hansen et al. 2013). These platforms allow scientists to update vegetation maps and detect structural changes such as

deforestation or habitat fragmentation. By integrating traditional field research with satellite imagery, phytocoenology now provides the precise, up-to-date data necessary for effective nature conservation and spatial planning. This research integrates remote sensing and machine learning to enhance spatial data quality for forest management and the predictive mapping of phytocoenological communities.

2 Materials and methods

This research proposes a method for mapping phytocoenological forest communities within the territory of the Republic of Croatia. The existing map of phytocoenological forest communities is used as a foundation for machine learning, to improve results, the use of the available land cover map from the European Space Agency (ESA) is proposed. By integrating satellite imagery from the Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 (HLS) dataset with collected spatial data (Claverie et al. 2018), a basis is established for generating highly accurate maps. All of satellite imagery has been downloaded and preprocessed using Google Earth Engine (Gorelick et al. 2017).

2.1 Phytocoenological Map

The quality of maintenance systems and tools for forest communities influences the expansion and contraction of forests. The provided map of phytocoenological forest communities within the ALCAR project dates back to the early 21st century. This phytocoenological map was developed based on several years of field observations and forest type research conducted at the Croatian Forest Research Institute, which were integrated into the "Dynamic Geoinformation Display of Forest Ecosystems of the Republic of Croatia" through the STIRP technological project (funded by the Ministry of Science and Technology of the Republic of Croatia from 2003 to 2007, involving the Faculty of Geodesy and the Jastrebarsko Forest Research Institute). The map (Figure 1) contains 66 phytocoenological "communities present within the territory of the Republic of Croatia, with the total mapped area of these forest communities covering 2,670,383 ha (Gračan et al. 2002). Figure 1 illustrates the phytocoenological map within a narrowed area of interest for the visualization of preliminary research. Table 1 (Appendix A) serves as an illustrative example of the collected tabular data for this narrowed area, providing a

more detailed description and the specific definitions of the class numbers displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Phytocoenological communities of study area (Gračan et al. 2002), background SGA DOF 2022/2023.

2.2 Satellite imagery

The Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 (HLS) dataset provides consistent, analysis-ready surface reflectance products by aligning Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2 observations in space, time, and spectral characteristics. This harmonization increases the temporal frequency of available imagery, enabling near-global observations at a 30-meter spatial resolution every 2-3 days, which is highly useful for monitoring vegetation dynamics, land cover changes, and agricultural practices. HLS is particularly beneficial for applications that require both high spatial detail and frequent satellite revisits, such as monitoring crop phenology and studying ecosystems (Claverie et al. 2018). To ensure data quality, we selected satellite imagery with less than 10% cloud cover. The study employed a phenological approach selecting eight images from March to October of 2024 to capture the start, peak, and end of the growing season within one annual cycle.

2.3 ESA Land cover

The European Space Agency (ESA) dataset, ESA WorldCover 10 m, provides global land cover maps at a 10-meter resolution, developed based on Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite data. It offers detailed and consistent information on land cover types, enabling applications in environmental monitoring, climate modeling, biodiversity research, and sustainable land management. Due to its high spatial resolution and annual updates, ESA

WorldCover supports decision making at both local and global levels (Zanaga et al. 2021).

2.4 Classification

Random forest classification has become standard method for classification in remote sensing for its accuracy and ability to process complex, high-dimensional satellite data in terms of spatial and time resolution without overfitting. Final models created from random forest classification provides reliable classification for vegetation mapping and change detection. Based on decision trees, random forest is robust method that captures non-linear changes between spectral indices and land cover class (Belgiu and Drăguț 2016).

Support Vector Machines (SVM) classification is strongly recommended in remote sensing for its strong generalization capabilities. SVM model provides high accuracy with satellite imagery datasets and limited training samples. Final results are characterized by robustness although SVM is sensitive to hyperparameter tuning, it excels at capturing the non-linear patterns essential for precise vegetation and forest mapping (Mountrakis et al. 2011).

2.5 Samples for classification

Samples were created as random points within each phytocoenological community polygon according to a formula of 0.3/ha (Figure 2). This formula was introduced so that the sample distribution corresponds to the prevalence of each community within the area of interest. During the sample creation process, the ESA land cover map was used to isolate exclusively forest areas. By intersecting the samples generated from the community polygons with the ESA land cover, all points that do not spatially fall within the forest cover (according to the ESA dataset) were excluded.

Figure 2. Classification sample points (sp).

3 Results and Discussion

Spatial results (Figure 4) for both classifications aligned well with reference data and field observations, capturing both large-scale spatial patterns and subtle intra-community variability. Accuracy of classification is

Figure 3. SVM classification results.

Figure 4. Random forest classification results.

determined by F1 score values (Foody 2002). F1 is critical metric because it provides balanced view of classification. F1 score is calculated from the values of precision and recall: precision shows probability of classified pixel is actually representative of that category on the ground; and recall show probability that a certain area on the ground is classified as such. To understand how good classifications are working, macro average and weighted average are calculated. The macro average is the simple arithmetic mean of a metric across all classes and treats every class as equal. The weighted average calculates the mean of a metric, but it weights each class's contribution based on number of actual occurrences of that class in dataset. Used classifications yielded an overall accuracy of 53% as shown in Tables 2 and 3, for support vector machine and random forest models, respectively. Weighted F1-scores 0.45 for SVM and 0.48 for RF model and macro average 0.21 for SVM and 0.27 for RF suggest that accuracy is heavily influenced by a few dominant classes rather than a robust identification of all forest types. These results are expected because study area contains more than 20 different communities in very small area. The disparity between the weighted average precision 0.53 for SVM and 0.57 for RF model is minimal, however, the macro average precision 0.2 for SVM and 0.23 for RF mode, which is significant drop in value, indicating that the created model struggles to identify minority classes. The confusion matrices further illustrate this imbalance. Both models exhibit a strong bias toward the majority class (Class 25), frequently misclassifying rarer communities as this dominant type. While the weighted average precision is similar between the two models (0.53 for SVM, 0.57 for RF), the Random Forest (figure 4.) demonstrates a clearer advantage in handling the minority classes. The SVM (Figure 3, Table 2) almost entirely ignores the rarest communities, prioritizing brute-force accuracy on the common ones. Conversely, the Random Forest, though still impacted by the majority class, is less aggressively biased and successfully recovers patterns for several minority classes (e.g., Classes 13 and 19) that the SVM missed entirely. Consequently, the Random Forest provides a slightly more robust

identification across the diverse forest types (Figure 4, Table 3).

Table 2. SVM classification results.

	precision	recall	F1-score	support
accuracy			0.53	7306
macro avg	0.35	0.2	0.21	7306
weighted avg	0.53	0.53	0.45	7306

Table 3. Random forest classification results.

	precision	recall	F1-score	support
accuracy			0.53	7306
macro avg	0.58	0.23	0.27	7306
weighted avg	0.57	0.53	0.48	7306

4 Conclusions

This research demonstrates the application and integration of remote sensing methods as well as machine learning capabilities for the purpose of maintaining spatial data quality within the field of forestry sciences. The mapping of phytocoenological communities presented in this work delivers data that primarily serves the management of forest units, but also enables retrospective mapping to uncover trends, establish models, and make potential predictions for specific forest phytocoenological communities. The possibilities explored here place geodesy and geoinformatics in an interdisciplinary position, aimed at providing spatial data and collection methods to other disciplines. Forestry demands levels of spatial accuracy that geodesists fulfil by utilizing publicly available satellite missions.

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6 Appendix A

Table 1. Phytocoenological communities of study area (Gračan et al. 2002).

Forest Class	Plant Community Name	Soil Type
12	Montane beech forest with dead-nettle (<i>Lamio orvalae-Fagetum sylvaticae</i>)	Rendzina on dolomite
13	Montane beech forest with dead-nettle (<i>Lamio orvalae-Fagetum sylvaticae</i>)	Hillslope pseudogley
15	Montane beech forest with dead-nettle (<i>Lamio orvalae-Fagetum sylvaticae</i>)	Dystric brown soil
18	Sessile oak forest with wood-rush (<i>Luzulo-Quercetum petraeae</i>)	Dystric brown soil, shallow and medium deep
19	Sessile oak and sweet chestnut forest (<i>Quercu-Castaneetum sativae</i>)	Dystric brown soil (two-layered profiles)
20	Illyrian sessile oak and common hornbeam forest (<i>Epitrimio-Carpinetum betuli</i>)	Rendzina on marl and soft limestone
21	Illyrian sessile oak and common hornbeam forest	Eutric brown soil
22	Illyrian sessile oak and common hornbeam forest	Calcicambisol
23	Illyrian sessile oak and common hornbeam forest	Dystric brown soil
25	Illyrian sessile oak and common hornbeam forest	Hillslope pseudogley
26	Illyrian sessile oak and common hornbeam forest	Luvisol on unconsolidated sediments
28	Downy oak and South European flowering ash forest (<i>Ostryo-Quercetum pubescentis</i>)	Rendzina
30	Willow and poplar forests (<i>Salici-Populetum s. lat.</i>)	Alluvial soil, recent
31	Black alder forest with alder buckthorn (<i>Frangulo-Alnetum glutinosae</i> Rauš 1968)	Amphigley
33	Pedunculate oak forest with Dyer's greenweed (<i>Genisto elatae-Quercetum roboris</i>)	Amphigley
36	Pedunculate oak and common hornbeam forest (<i>Carpino betuli-Quercetum</i>)	Lowland pseudogley
37	Pedunculate oak and common hornbeam forest	Luvisol on unconsolidated sediments
38	Pedunculate oak and common hornbeam forest	Hypogley
41	Beech forest with European hop-hornbeam (<i>Ostryo-Fagetum</i>)	Rendzina on dolomite